

Composite Materials – Global Technology of the Past, Present and Future

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The field of fiber-reinforced composite materials has been a global pursuit from its very beginning in the early 1950s. In the UK, Anthony Kelly was a pioneer in understanding the importance of new innovations in high performance materials to the global society. In Japan, Hayashi pioneered the field of fiber composites as an opportunity to develop new materials for aeronautical applications, but it was not until the PAN based carbon fiber was invented in the 1960s in the United Kingdom by Watt and in Japan by Shindo that true promise of fiber-reinforced composites was assured. Today the field of carbon fiber composites dominates military aircraft and appears on the threshold of a similar accomplishment in civil aviation with the development of the Boeing 787 and Airbus 350 aircraft.

Indeed, it is the growth in the simulation capability based in computing power that has been responsible for much of the recent success in the field and that will provide the vehicle for significant advances in structural analysis, design and manufacturing in the future. The advancement of computing power during the past forty years has followed the miniaturization of computer hardware described in Moore's Law, that the number of transistors that can be inexpensively placed on an integrated circuit is increasing exponentially, doubling approximately every two years. The observation was first made by Intel co-founder Gordon E. Moore. The trend has continued for more than half a century and is expected to continue for another decade at least and perhaps much longer.

There is no doubt that computing power has grown exponentially during the past four decades and this trend is expected to accelerate. The gigaflop barrier was surpassed in 1988/9 and the teraflop barrier in 1996/7. The next step will be the petaflop barrier (10^{15} floating-point operations per second). If the growth in computer power since the turn of the century is examined, several important computational levels are predicted to be achieved within the next fifty years. The computational rate in 1970 was 1 calculation per second per \$1000 and by 2010 it will exceed 10,000,000,000. At the present rate of growth, computational power will reach that of the mouse brain this year, the human brain by 2024 and all human brains by 2048.

If conventional 70 nm lithography technology is followed, the number chips and power consumption of the next generation computer would likely be excessive, but innovations in nanotechnology and nanostructured novel materials, such as carbon nanotubes, to replace transistors and diodes, and quantum mechanics offer the potential for sustained growth in computing power.

The second tool empowered by the extraordinary growth in computing power is molecular modeling. Heisenberg published his first paper on quantum mechanics in 1925 (*Z. Phys.*, 1925, 33, 879) to begin the quantum age, but the modeling of molecules of interest had to wait for the advent and development of modern high speed computing. Indeed, by 1970, the computational power available still lagged significantly behind the demands of molecular modeling. Yet by 1974, Robert Langridge, et.al. published a paper on the use of computer graphics to visualize three-dimensional chemical structures (Langridge, R.; *Fed. Proc. Fed. Am. Soc. Exp. Biol.*, 1974, 33: 2332). The first issue of the *Journal of Computational Chemistry* was not published until 1980. What followed thereafter was the continuous introduction of new software and corporations for the sale and support of that software. In 1989 Cambridge Molecular Design was founded in Cambridge, UK by Patrick Coulter with the Cerius family of software products for molecular modeling and materials design. As new corporations and software were introduced over the next decade, some did not survive, while others were merged. In 2001, Accelrys emerged as a subsidiary of Pharmacoepia by combining Molecular Simulations, Synopsis Scientific Systems, and Oxford Molecular Group. LAMMPS, Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator, developed by Sandia National Laboratories now offers a broad range in molecular modeling capability that represents the current state of the art.

The present paper will describe examples of advances in computational methods at the atomistic, nano, micro and meso levels with the goal of establishing bridges between the scales that allow the nanoscale to be directly linked to the macroscopic scale with extraordinary increases in simulation fidelity. These results will give future engineers the potential to certify flight composite vehicles directly by analysis and significantly reduce the scale of experimental tests and the costs of certification.